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Low-Frequency EIS for PEM Fuel-Cell Diagnostics

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

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Outline

- About the Giantleap project and FC system Topology
- Degradation - Observed by polarization curve
- Degradation – Observed by EIS
- Key feature: The development of the Low Frequency intercept
- Method for on-line automatic- detection of Low frequency intercept
- Summary

GIANTLEAP

Giantleap Improved Automation of Non-polluting Transportation with Lifetime Extension of Automotive PEM fuel cells

Call topic: **FCH-01.2-2015**
Diagnostics and control for increased fuel cell system lifetime in automotive applications

Project dates:

01/05/2016 – 30/04/2019

Total project budget: **3,26 M€**

Targets & Deliverables

- Enhance understanding of component degradation
- Develop appropriate monitoring & diagnostic methods
- Develop cost-effective control methods
- Implement developed diagnostics & control systems in a prototype (bus) focused on power management
- Demonstrate and validate the implementations in relevant environment

Bus FC system topology

Prognostics and Health Monitoring

Problem:

- Fuel Cell performance degrades over time:
- How to diagnose it in time and efficiency in a real-life application

Objective:

- Use a set of performance indicators to monitor and predict development that can be used for enhancing the operation

Focus here:

- Automatic monitoring of one such parameter:

The real axis Low Frequency Intercept from EIS

Degradation with time /load cycles

Development of the polarization curve with increasing number of load cycles

"Poor man's prognostics":

Method:

Estimate polarization curve development from actual operating data and estimate the performance at a normalized current level

Degradation observed by full EIS

Observe development of the low frequency intercept point. (where the $\text{Im}(Z)=0$)

Ageing/wear has a significant impact on the low frequency intercept

Application of impedance model to fuel cell degradation study

A novel 11-element equivalent circuit model [] capable of yielding experimentally obtained low-frequency inductive behavior [**]*

[*] Pivac, I., Šimić, B., Barbir, F.: *Experimental diagnostics and modeling of inductive phenomena at low frequencies in impedance spectra of proton exchange membrane fuel cells*, Journal of Power Sources, 365, 2017, 240–248.

[**] Pivac, I., Barbir, F.: *Inductive phenomena at low frequencies in impedance spectra of proton exchange membrane fuel cells – A review*, Journal of Power Sources, 326, 2016, 112–119.

Application of impedance model to fuel cell degradation study

Comparison of measured and simulated impedance spectra at 0.6 A cm^{-2} during the AST

- simulation results show very good agreement with experimental data
- LF intercept (Total $R=R_0+R_1+R_2+R_3+R_4$) increased most significantly

Method for identification of $|Z|$ when $\text{Im}(Z(j\omega))=0$

"Poor man's EIS": Identify the single point of low frequency intercept

Use relay feedback excitation to establish small limit-cycle oscillation at desired (unknown) frequency

Analysis based on "Describing function" theory and Fourier series analysis

Used e.g. for controller tuning [Ref. Åström & Hägglund 1984]

Use of relay excitation to identify where $\text{Im}(Z(j\omega))=0$

Voltage $u(s)=Z(s)*I(s)$

Add filter $d(s)=1/s^2$ (double integrator)

$H(s)=Z(s)/s^2$ for the relay excitation

Phase at the critical frequency of $H(s)$

$$\angle H(j\omega_{H180}) = -180^\circ$$

\Rightarrow

$$\angle Z(j\omega_{H180}) = 0^\circ$$

The impedance can be easily calculated from voltage and current data during the cycling at the desired frequency

Unknown:

Frequency and amplitude

Simulink diagram for relay excitation scheme

Signals in
Online R-estimator

Z: Impedance model (from EIS)
Shape filter: $d(s)=d1 \times d2$

Relay **input** & **output** signal

Current input value (delta)
(pre-filter $d1(s)$'s output)

Measured voltage
(with bias & noise)

On-line impedance estimate
(ca 0.03Ω)

Bias estimate
[time unit: seconds]

FC impedance in Nyquist diagram with estimated result

Estimated
LF intercept

Step responses

Observation:

The initial overshoot peak in voltage after a step in current is also an indicator of R_{max}

(Here at $\omega = 2.14$ rad/sec)

The use of low-pass prefilter reduce the transient impact and avoids steps in current.

The 1st order filter

$$d_1(s) = 1/(1 + T_f * s)$$

Steepest slope = $\Delta I / T_f$ [A/sec]

E.g.: select $T_f = \Delta I / (\text{Max slope})$

Summary

- Ageing has an impact on the low frequency intercept with the real axis in the Nyquist diagram of the Fuel Cell impedance (as obtained by a full EIS).
- The proposed method for "measurement" of the actual FC impedance on this "point" is to use so-called relay feedback that establishes a stable limit cycle at the desired frequency and amplitude. The impedance can be identify directly during the experiment
- Adjustments and corrections may be one by standard Fourier series method on the recorded data.
- The algorithm can be implemented in the basic Fuel Cell Control Unit, and scheduled to be executed at suitable time intervals and a set of standardized operating conditions (e.g. coordinated with polarization curve recordings)

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